

THE EVOLUTION OF CHANGES IN THE MANAGEMENT OF NATURAL HEALING ASSETS

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Abstract. The article analyzes the evolutionary changes in the institutional support and management systems of natural healing assets at the stages of the state's economic development. The main trends and imbalances are identified, and, based on international experience, recommendations are given for changes to the Regulations on the Activities of the Main Authorities in order to exercise clearer control over the extraction, use and restoration of natural healing assets (NHA). For the first time, an interdepartmental model of the NHA life cycle has been developed with a clear division of responsibility between the Geonadra, the Ministry of Health, the State Social Protection Agency, the Ministry of Environment and the Municipalities, taking into account world practices (WHO, GWI, EU directives, the experience of France, Japan, the USA).

The essential content of the unified state electronic geoinformation system for subsoil use has been improved in terms of the mechanism for digital integration of all processes through NHA, open geoportals and public registers, which forms a single information space in the field of natural resources.

The financial and organizational mechanism for managing natural assets without additional budget costs has been determined by diversifying funding sources (special funds, National Health Insurance Fund, license fees, private funds).

The proposed system of amendments to the current regulations of the central executive bodies of Ukraine allows for the implementation of a system-coordinated approach to the management of natural healing assets (NHA) without the creation of new institutions. This strengthens interdepartmental coordination, transparency and efficiency of the use of NHA in the post-war reconstruction of the country, and also brings Ukraine closer to European standards in the field of rehabilitation, health care and nature management.

Relevance. According to the Ukraine Recovery Program, which is part of the public investment reform for the restoration of critical infrastructure, as well as improving the welfare of the population as a result of war events, 225 projects with a total value of more than 500 mln are currently being implemented. But all these programs by nature of the project are related only to new construction, reconstruction, modernization and purchase of goods. Information data shows (*Projects, 2025*) that no program according to the planned funding is dedicated to natural assets.

The Recovery Plan of Ukraine for 2023-2025 includes 17 programs worth 350 billion USD, 3 of which are focused on environmental protection, with a total

funding of 135 billion USD. However, if we consider the projects within the programs themselves, the following trends can be observed. The Restoration of a Clean and Protected Environment Project (*Restoration of a Clean and Protected Environment, 2023*) includes 70 programs, 18 of which relate to the preservation and restoration of natural resources and the use of natural assets. The Modernization of the Healthcare System Project (*Modernization of the Healthcare System, 2023*) includes 50 programs, 3 of which are related to rehabilitation. The Energy Independence and Green Course Project (*Energy Independence and Green Course, 2023*) includes 30 programs related only to energy and oil. Thus, existing funding does not cover recovery needs for rehabilitation, restoration, and sustainable use of natural assets.

The use of natural assets in post-war recovery according to international experience indicates that the assets themselves play a significant role in post-war economic growth. Thus, (*Lang, 2000*) in Vietnam, 2.5 billion US dollars were spent on the post-war revival of natural assets - the budget of the National Reforestation Program for 5 million hectares (1998–2010), of which 1.5 billion US dollars were spent as international assistance (donor grants), the rest - 1.0 billion US dollars - state funding. Iraq (*Wenger, 2004*), spent 11 million US dollars - the Mesopotamian Marshes Restoration Project (2004) for the financial resources of the Japanese government through the UN Trust Fund (*UNEP Wetlands Restoration Project*). Bosnia and Herzegovina (*Causevic et al., 2022*) 545.6 million US dollars USA – international environmental financing (2015–2020) mainly for water, energy and waste. 58% in the form of grants and - 38% in the form of concessional loans. Main donors: World Bank (188 million, 34%), German government (BMZ, - 155 million, 28%), European Commission (71 million, 13%) and Sweden (53 million, 10%). Rwanda (*Rwanda Green Fund – FONERWA / Rwanda, 2018*) approximately 130 million USD. US – the volume of the Rwanda Green Fund (FONERWA) for “green” restoration projects international donors (main ones – the UK government, the Green Climate Fund, etc.) filled the national environmental fund, which finances reforestation, water and sustainable agriculture. Lebanon (*Tamer - Chammas, 2012*) 11.7 million USD. USA – early environmental recovery programs after the conflict in 2006 UN/UNDP: \$2 million for urgent repair of water and sewage networks; EU (ECHO) and UNDP: - \$9.7 million for a renewable energy project (CEDRO) to replace destroyed energy infrastructure. Serbia (FR Yugoslavia) (*Thummarukudy and etc., 2013*) \$12.5 million – spent on cleaning up industrial sites contaminated during the 1999 war. Voluntary contributions from 10 European donor countries through the UNEP program (estimated need was \$20 million) Donors: Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Norway, Sweden, Switzerland.

Regarding post-war recovery, currently Ukrainian legislation includes (*On Approval of the State Target Program for Comprehensive Water Supply of Territories Affected by Military Actions for the Period Until 2030, 2024*) The State Target Program for Comprehensive Water Supply of Territories Affected by Military Actions (until 2030) for 9 regions of Dnipropetrovsk, Kirovohrad,

Donetsk, Zaporizhzhia, Luhansk, Mykolaiv, Odessa, Kharkiv and Kherson regions, which will be aimed at restoring and constructing water supply systems, repairing hydraulic structures damaged by the war; using groundwater to diversify water sources and financing from the state budget of UAH 54.19 billion. The Presidential Program "Green Country" (a billion trees) (*State Agency of Forest Resources of Ukraine - Green Country, 2021*) is aimed at planting 1 billion trees in 3 years; increasing the area of forests by 1 million hectares over 10 years; restoring forests and afforestation throughout the country, in particular in war-affected territories, financed from the state budget. The National Program for the Development of the Mineral and Raw Materials Base of Ukraine until 2030 (updated version adopted in 2024) provides for the exploration and development of mineral deposits, especially critical and strategic ones; ecologization of subsoil use, digitalization of geological information; attracting investments in the extraction of strategic minerals and is financed from the state budget.

International initiatives currently include EU4Green Recovery East (EU program for Eastern Partnership countries) (*UA Home page, 2024*) Green reconstruction after war damage: supporting Ukraine on the path to "green" reconstruction according to EU standards, implementing a circular economy, improving water resource management, reducing water depletion, developing eco-data; supporting small and medium-sized businesses in increasing resource efficiency and creating "green" jobs for 2025-2028 with total EU funding of 21.3 million euros per region). The project "Natural Heritage for Life in Ukraine" (LIFE) 2024-2026 (*Ukrinform, 2024*) The first LIFE project in Ukraine: expanding the Emerald Network and its transition to the European Natura 2000 network. The Global Environment Facility (GEF) - supporting the restoration of nature after environmental restoration. thus, funding for projects to restore ecosystems, improve water policy, chemical safety, and air quality is being considered.

Based on the above data, we have reproduced a comparative table of natural resource restoration programs (Table 1).

Table 1 – Natural resource recovery programs in countries recovering from war

Country / program	Funding amount	Funding sources	Advantages	Disadvantages
Vietnam – Reforestation Program	2.5 billion USD (1998–2010)	1.5 billion – international aid, 1.0 billion – state budget	Scalability, sustainability, donor support	Long implementation period, weak quality control on the ground
Iraq – Mesopotamian Marshes Restoration	11 million USD (2004)	Government of Japan through UN fund (UNEP)	International cooperation, ecosystem value	Small budget, limited scope for influence
Bosnia and Herzegovina	545.6 million USD (2015–2020)	World Bank, European Commission, BMZ, Sida	High funding, diversity of sources, multi-sectorality	Risk of duplication of projects, political delays

		(grants/loans)		
Rwanda – FONERWA	~130 million USD	Great Britain, Green Climate Fund, other donors	National fund, sustainable practices, ecological focus	Dependence on external funding
Lebanon – CEDRO	11.7 million USD (after 2006)	UN, EU, UNDP	Restoration of water and energy infrastructure	Weak program coordination, vulnerability to new conflicts
Serbia (FR Yugoslavia)	12.5 million USD	10 donor countries through UNEP	International mobilization, decontamination	Need for more funds (20 million was needed)
Ukraine – Water Supply Program	54.19 billion UAH (1.35 billion USD)	State budget	National scale, focus on war-affected areas	Lack of environmental rehabilitation component
Ukraine – Green Country	Not specified (state budget)	State Agency of Forest Resources	Eco-orientation, billion trees, long-term	Lack of clear impact analysis, monitoring risks
Ukraine – Mineral and Raw Material Base by 2030	Not specified	State budget	Industrial value, digitalization of subsoil use	Focus on extraction, not on environmental restoration
Ukraine – EU4Green Recovery	21.3 million EUR per region	EU	Focus on "green" projects, support for SMEs	Limited funding, only for 2025–2028
Ukraine – LIFE / Natura 2000	Not specified	EU (LIFE), GEF	Integration into the Natura 2000 network, international support	Initial implementation stage, need for localization of standards

Compiled based on data from: Lang, 2000, Wenger, 2004, Causevic et al., 2022, Rwanda Green Fund – FONERWA / Rwanda, 2018, Tamer - Chammas, 2012, Thummarukudy and etc., 2013, On approval of the State Target Program for Integrated Water Supply of Territories Affected by Military Actions for the Period Until 2030, 2024, State Forest Resources Agency of Ukraine - Green Country, 2021, UA Main page, 2024, Ukrinform, 2024.

The above allows us to draw the following conclusions regarding the management of natural assets in post-war reconstruction, namely:

The existing international practice regarding the post-war reconstruction of natural resource potential, and the already established domestic program solutions prove the need to analyze the evolutionary changes in the management of natural assets in the post-war perspective, especially those that are therapeutic and can be used for rehabilitation and recovery needs.

- hybrid financing (state budget + international donors), which increases the sustainability and scale of projects (Vietnam, Rwanda, Bosnia);

- ecological orientation and green transformation (programs such as Green Recovery, Green Country, LIFE/Natura 2000);

- multisectoral approach - programs with the integration of water, energy, forest and agricultural components have a wider impact (Bosnia, Rwanda, Lebanon).

- the use of national funds (FONERWA) ensures resource mobilization and strategic planning, potentially useful for Ukraine.

Currently, the more effective in Ukraine is the national management model (3 programs) aimed at restoring natural assets. As for post-war restoration, a vivid example is Iraq, Serbia, Lebanon, also 3 programs under the international management model, in which control over the implementation of programs belongs to donors. In second place for the restoration of natural assets, a mixed management model is used. However, such a model has high risks associated with institutional barriers. The EU/GEF models (LIFE, EU4Green), which have become widespread recently, require bringing domestic standards of environmental rehabilitation to the EU level.

There are also significant disparities associated with uneven funding, infrastructure restoration without an environmental component, as well as poorly developed mechanisms for assessing effectiveness and control.

In this study, by natural healing assets we mean natural healing resources and related services that are involved, or can be involved, in economic activities by entities in the resort economy.

In the context of modern trends and conceptual directions of development and war in Ukraine, the management of natural healing assets (NHA) has undergone profound structural and functional changes. The evolution of approaches to NMA management from administrative-command to post-industrial and the search for sustainable forms of strategic management is currently accompanied by numerous challenges.

Table 2 - Main trends in NHA management by stages of economic development

Period	Type of economy	Approach to NHA	Policies / regulations	Examples of projects
before 1991	Brown (industrial)	Operational-medical	- SanPiN on mineral waters- Resolution on resorts	- Program "Medical Resources"- Inventory of sanatoriums at the level of the union republics
1991–2005	Transitional	Unsystematic, sporadic	- Law "On resorts" (2000)- Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine No. 195 (1996) on sanitary protection zones	- Partial privatization of sanatoriums
2006–2019	Green (by European integration)	Ecological-recreational	- Tourism development strategy (2008)- National report on the state of the environment (annually)	- Program "Tourist Ukraine"- Projects of GIS zoning of natural territories
2020–2022	Resource-based	Natural-capital	- Presidential Decree "On the ecosystem	- "Green Country" (1 billion trees)- Pilots of

			approach..." (2020)- State strategies for the digitalization of subsoil use	the digital cadastre of mineral waters
from 2023	Renewable	Rehabilitation-integrative	- State strategy for regional development until 2027- EU4Green Recovery action plan	- EU4Green Recovery (2023–2028)- Restoration of PLA in Mykolaiv, Kharkiv, Zakarpattia regions

Let us dwell on each of the periods in more detail. Thus, the stage of the brown (industrial) economy (Table 3) can be characterized by centralized management, strict regulation of access to resources, integration with the health care system. Natural healing resources were used in medicine. Thus, the Resolution "Regulations on Resorts" (September 5, 1973, No. 654) defined the types of resorts according to natural healing resources (mineral, balneological, climatic, etc.) and introduced a mandatory sanitary and health regime, which provided for the protection of sources, the cleanliness of areas and the use of PCR in treatment. At the same time, control and management were carried out in such a way that the Ministry of Health issued approval for the opening of resorts, trade unions exercised control over social guarantees and prevention standards.

Local authorities controlled development and established restrictions on economic activity. The activities and boundaries of the resorts "Berezivskie mineralni vody", "Synyak", "Truskavets", "Slovyansk" were carried out by Resolutions on the territory of sanitary protection, land use regime, rules for the development of resort areas. Also, requirements for the placement, design and operation of recreational and medical facilities (sanatoriums, resorts) were carried out by DSanPiN, and further control was carried out by local authorities.

Table 3 - Overview of regulatory acts on natural healing assets (THA) during the brown economy period

Regulatory act	Topics
Resolution of the Council of Ministers of the Ukrainian SSR of 1960 No. 606	Transfer of sanatoriums, rest homes to trade unions
Resolution of the Council of Ministers of the Ukrainian SSR of 1973 No. 654	Approval of the "Regulations on resorts" - mechanisms for the creation, protection, development and operation of resorts
Resolution of the Council of Ministers of the Ukrainian SSR of 1973 No. 654	Regulations on resorts; regulation of land use and design
Resolution of the Council of Ministers of the Ukrainian SSR of 1982 No. 490	Approval of the Regulations on individual resort territories (Polyana, Soymy, etc.)
Resolution of the Council of Ministers of the Ukrainian SSR of 1982 No. 421	Approval of the Regulations on the resorts "Berezivskie Mineralnye Vody" and "Synyak" - resort territories, protection zones, sanitary regimes
Resolution of the Ukrainian SSR of 1982 No. 614	Regulations on the resorts "Truskavets" and "Slovyansk" - similar in structure and norms
DSanPiN 172-96	Sanitary rules for the placement, design, operation of health facilities (resorts, sanatoriums)

During the period of the brown economy (until 1991), resorts and sanatoriums were regulated through multi-level regulations and sanitary rules. Control was exercised through a system of specialized bodies - the Ministry of Health, sanitary and epidemiological services, architectural services, local councils and trade unions, i.e. there was centralized management, strict regulation of access to resources, integration with the health care system. The management model of this period.

The economic system of this period is characterized by a command-administrative manifestation, with centralized planning and state ownership of all natural resources. The management bodies in this period were only (Fig. 1) at the central level: the Ministry of Health coordinated medical policy, developed standards, the Trade Union controlled and distributed resources and finances for rehabilitation and health improvement. Financing of health improvement, rehabilitation and management of NHA was carried out at the expense of the budget and the Social Insurance Fund. NHA was considered national wealth, but was actually monopolized by the state without mechanisms for economic assessment or stimulation of their preservation. Monitoring and control were carried out through sanitary and epidemiological stations, health authorities, commissions for the distribution of vouchers, without tools for assessing efficiency or investment attractiveness. At the state level, management was reduced only to the implementation of central-level plans without independent management policy. Local authorities were only executors with vertical accountability and with the requirement to meet planned indicators. That is, the complete absence of economic incentives, market institutions, and neglect of natural capital.

Figure 1 - Management bodies of the resort economy from the point of view of rehabilitation, health improvement and NHA (period before 1991)

Regarding the management of NHA during the brown economy period, the main resort department of the Ministry of Health kept records in cooperation with the Geological Survey and the State Environmental Protection Agency regarding the certification of NHA, balance reserves, sanitary passports of sources, and the act of approval of reserves. At the same time, a centralized register was maintained, and annual reports were submitted to the Ministry of Health. Permission for use was granted only by the central authority. Control over the use of NHA was ensured through the following controlling bodies:

- SES - control of the sanitary condition of sources, laboratory analyses of water composition, temperatures, levels of trace elements;
- Ministry of Health (central or state level) - approved the regime of use of sources, flow restrictions, seasonal load schedules;
- State Geological Service - study of reserves, hydrogeological mapping, accounting for changes in well productivity;
- Research institutes - methodology of use, medical and biological assessment of PCR efficiency, creation of a regulatory framework.

From the point of view of management requirements and generalizing reporting forms, we have compiled (*Krupka & Porokhnavets, 2019*), (*Ognyanyk, M. S. 2000*) (*Law of Ukraine On Accounting and Financial Reporting in Ukraine, 2000*) a typical form of accounting for a natural medicinal resource (using the example of mineral water) for this period had the following form (table 4).

Table 4 – Typical form of accounting for a natural healing assets (using the example of mineral water)

1. General information	
Field	Contents
Resource name	Source No. 1 "Morshynska"
Geographical location	Region, district, geographical coordinates
Resource type	Mineral water / therapeutic mud / radon source / climatic factor
Record keeping body	Main Department of Resorts of the Ministry of Health / Geological Service / SES
Balance holder	Sanatorium, resort, local health department
Year of opening or operation	- 1990
Cadastral number (inventory)	Internal registration code in the system of the Ministry of Health / State Geological Supervision
2. Hydrogeological characteristics (of the healing resource)	
Water type	Chloride-sodium, sulfate, hydrocarbonate, etc.
Mineralization	g/l (e.g. 6.2 g/l)
Outlet temperature	°C
Well depth	m
Flow rate (productivity)	m ³ /day
Operation mode	Continuous / seasonal / mixed
Horizon protection level	Artesian, interlayer, etc.

State Geological Supervision report	Act on approval of reserves (e.g. Protocol No. ... of ... year)
3. Sanitary and epidemiological characteristics	
Status of the protected area	Equipped / absent / partially
Presence of a sanitary passport	No., date of issue, by whom issued
Results of the latest analysis	Content of microorganisms, impurities, compliance with GOST
Recommended medical use	For the treatment of the gastrointestinal tract / liver / kidneys / musculoskeletal system
Contraindications	Yes / No (clarification according to medical indications)
4. Operational and legal status	
Availability of a permit for use	Resolution / order of the Ministry of Health or government body
Limitations in the mode of use	For example, no more than 80 m ³ /day
Project organization / year of last reconstruction	Name, date
User information	Sanatorium, subordination to the trade union / Ministry of Health / local council
Availability of an automated accounting system	Yes / No (for wells - meters)
5. Therapeutic and biological efficacy (according to medical research)	
Typical indications	For example: chronic gastritis, liver disease
Methods of application	Drinking treatment, baths, irrigation
Duration of the course	18 -21 days
Results of research by the research institute	References to scientific studies
Certification of the method	Year, document

Also, a well passport with technical characteristics was additionally maintained, an inventory of sources was carried out every 5 years, and a report was sent to the Ministry of Health annually on use, volumes, and sanitary condition.

The next period was a transitional, chaotic economy of 1991–2005. characterized by the privatization of assets without proper assessment of the resource base, chaotic regional management (table 5). The two main laws regulating the use of natural resources, establishing requirements and standards for sanatoriums and resorts were: the Law of Ukraine "On Environmental Protection",

1991, No. 1264-XII, which determined that natural healing resources are recognized as objects of protection, and Articles 16–19 establish direct regulation of the extraction, protection, inventory, and licensing of natural resources. Control over the impact assessment, licensing, and authorization of field development is carried out by the central environmental protection authorities. The next law was the Law of Ukraine "On Resorts" dated 05.10.2000, No. 2026-III, which is a profile law on the use of PCR, requirements for resorts and treatment. This law defines the concept of a resort, natural healing resources, the procedure for creating resort territories, establishes the regime of use, protection, accounting and state regulation of activities in the field of balneology. Control is entrusted to the bodies of health, geology, environment and local self-government.

Table 5 - Overview of regulatory legal acts on natural healing assets (NHA) in the period of transitional, chaotic economy

Regulatory and legal act	Subject
Law of Ukraine "On Environmental Protection" 1991	Defines the classification of natural resources (including medical and health-improving)
Law of Ukraine "On Provision of Sanatorium and Resort Treatment" 1991	Regulates the procedure for referral, compensation, benefits
Law of Ukraine "On Rehabilitation of Disabled Persons" 1991	Contains provisions on the creation of rehabilitation centers, infrastructure and PLA
Instructions of the Ministry of Health on the Organization of Referral to Sanatoriums 1991	Regulates the mechanism of medical selection, participation of doctors in referral
Law of Ukraine "On the Nature Reserve Fund" 1992 No. 2456-XII	Defines the legal regime for the protection of recreational and medical territories
Law of Ukraine "On the Status of War Veterans" 1993 No. 3551-12	Preferential sanatorium and resort treatment for veterans
Law of Ukraine "On Tourism" 1995 No. 324/95-VR	Regulation of tourism activities, including medical tourism
Law of Ukraine "On Victims of Nazi Persecution" 2000 No. 1584-14	Benefits for sanatorium and resort rehabilitation of victims
Law of Ukraine "On Resorts" 2000 No. 2026-III	Definition of NHA, conditions of use, creation of resorts, protected zones
Order of the State Commission for Mineral Resources "On Approval of the Instructions for the Application of the Classification of Mineral Reserves and Resources of the State Subsoil Fund to Deposits of Drinking and Technical Underground Waters" 2000 No. 23	Basic principles of assessment of prospective and forecast resources of drinking and technical groundwater within prospective areas and territories
Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine "On Approval of the Procedure for the Creation and Maintenance of the State Cadastre of Natural Therapeutic Resources 2001 No. 872	An electronic NHA cadastre has been created, data from the cadastre is used when making decisions on granting permits for the use of NHA.
Order of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine "Procedure for the Implementation of Medical and Biological Assessment of PCR" 2003 No. 243	The procedure for providing a balneological conclusion on the quality of a natural resource has been determined and mandatory medical-biological, hydrogeological, and resort studies have been introduced
Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of	Permits for the use of subsoil, including natural

Ukraine No. 827 “On Special Permits for the Use of Subsoil” 2005 No. 827	therapeutic resources
Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine No. 828 “Procedure for Auctions for the Sale of Permits” 2005 No. 828	Auctions for granting licenses with the approval of the Ministry of Health for natural therapeutic resources (PCR)
Land Code of Ukraine 2005	Regulation of the intended use of resort lands

During this period, a formal multi-level model was used, but with implementation failures. The legislation established a three-level model for the use of resort resources: of national importance (national SPAs and resorts), local importance (district springs, small sanatoriums); special regime (separate medical institutions: for the disabled, veterans, Chernobyl survivors). However, actual use indicates an imbalance in access, the majority of resources were used by state-owned enterprises, the private sector was almost excluded from access to SPAs (due to the complexity of obtaining a license, the conclusion of the Ministry of Health, assessment of reserves, etc.).

The period of the transitional economy (1991–2005) is characterized by the transition to a market model of management. The sphere of the resort economy of that stage is marked by elements of privatization of infrastructure (sanatorium and resort complexes) without the transfer of rights to SPAs. Natural resources are exclusively state property. The main management bodies are (Fig. 2): the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, the Ministry of Health of Ukraine (methodical control, licensing) - the State Geological Survey of Ukraine (recording and protection of deposits) - the Ministry of Ecoresources (permits for special water use) - SES (resource quality control). The contradictions of this period are institutional support due to the lack of a unified system for managing resorts: powers are divided between the Ministry of Health, the Ministry of Environmental Resources, the State Service for Geo-Subsoil, and local authorities. Mixed financing is also inherent in this period, but there is a partial state order for the rehabilitation of privileged categories of the population, and the financing of trade union vouchers is being reduced. There is also a lack of economic incentives for investing in environmental protection measures. However, there is a need for scientific developments for the use of NHA (development of a methodology, cadaster NHA expertise, certification of natural factors).

Figure 2. Management bodies of the resort economy from the point of view of rehabilitation, health improvement and NHA (period 1991 - 2005)

In the period 1991–2005, accounting and inventory of NHA were carried out through a combination of state, industry, and local levels. Accounting and inventory, namely (mineral water reserves (volume, flow rate, mineralization), points of exit and wells, chemical and microbiological composition, amount of water/mud used for the period:

- State Service for Geology and Mineral Resources (geological, cadastral accounting);
- Resorts and sanatoriums (internal technical accounting);
- SES (quality and safety of resources)
- Ministry of Health/UkrNII balneology (medical and biological documentation).

The accounting forms were: well/source passport, chemical analysis logs, workshop water production log, annual reports to the Ministry of Health, SES, geological services.

From the point of view of management requirements and generalizing reporting forms, we have compiled a typical form of accounting for a natural healing resource (using the example of mineral water) (Table 6) (mineral water, 1991–2005)

Table 6 - Typical form of accounting for a natural healing resource (using the example of mineral water)

Source (or well) passport	Source name Geographical location Well number Date of commissioning Depth, flow rate, type of mineralization Owner / balance holder
Journal of Water Chemical Analysis	Analysis date Temperature RH, mineralization Content of salts, iron, radon Laboratory signature and seal
Journal of Microbiological Control	Bacterial and Pathogen Content Periodicity According to SES Standards Results and Recommendations
Workshop water production accounting journal	Daily accounting (in m ³) Total per day / month Level of costs and losses Purpose: treatment / spillage / other
Sanitary passport of the facility	Issued by the SES Contained a description of the technical condition of the source, the protection zone, and recommendations for operation

The inventory was carried out to reassess the reserves once every 5 years and annual verification of the sanitary condition of the sources and when changing the use profile or transferring them to another institution.

The main trends of this period can be characterized as the beginning of decentralization in management, which led to imbalances associated with the

fragmentation of responsibility between different management bodies and duplication of powers. Also, balance and control data on the use of NHA are not summarized at the state level. Despite the fact that the period is characterized by privatization, additional investments are needed for infrastructure development, but the owners do not have the right to use NHA in these territories. Rehabilitation and rehabilitation also lost their social function and became commercialized, which led to limited access for the population.

This period is characterized by the irrational use of natural healing resources, which were exploited without revaluation of reserves or new hydrogeological studies. The State Cadastre of NHA was created only in 2001, but until 2005 it remained fragmented and incomplete.

The period of the green (according to European integration) economy (2006-2019) - the modernization stage is characterized by the emergence of tourism development programs, regional strategies, and fragmented application of environmental standards (Table 7).

Table 7 - Overview of regulatory acts on natural healing assets (NHA) in the period of the green economy

Regulatory act	Topics
Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine "On approval of the Procedure for the use of PCR" 2006 No. 754	Protection, surveying, technical inventory
Order of the Ministry of Health "On approval of methodological instructions" "Sanitary and virological control of water bodies" 2007 No. 284	Approved the procedure for certification of NHA
Instructions on the organization of the SCR in the UDO of Ukraine 2010	Procedure for granting permits to preferential categories
Water Code of Ukraine - Chapter 12 (amendments to Article 62) 2012 No. 5456-VI	Definition of therapeutic water bodies and the procedure for their inclusion in the official list
Strategy for the development of tourism and resorts until 2026 2017 Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine No. 168-r	The direction of "medical and health tourism" has been recorded
Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine "On approval of the Procedure for rehabilitation" 2018 No. 1057	A new approach to rehabilitation services

The period 2006–2019, the formation and implementation of the green economy is characterized by a mixed management model, the market for the provision of health and rehabilitation services is expanding, while the state regulates access to NHA, which remain the property of the people and are provided for use by business entities under a special permit. Institutional support remains the same as in the previous period, the functions of control and management are also still distributed: the Ministry of Health controls the issues of medicine and rehabilitation programs, the Ministry of Nature issues special permits for the use of NHA, the SES carries out control (Fig. 3).

As in previous periods, the revaluation of NHA reserves, confirmation of debits, and updating of passports were carried out once every 5 years with a well inventory act, which becomes the basis for further operation.

Figure 3. Management bodies of the resort economy from the point of view of rehabilitation, health improvement and PLA (period 2006 - 2019)

From the point of view of management requirements and generalizing reporting forms, we have compiled a typical form of accounting for a natural medicinal resource (using the example of mineral water) (mineral water, 2006–2019).

Table 8 - Typical form of accounting for a natural medicinal resource (using the example of mineral water)

Document	Description
NHA Passport	Technical and medical-biological characteristics of the natural source
Sanitary Passport	Approved by the SES based on laboratory tests
Operation Mode Project	Document regulating the volume and method of NHA extraction
Source Inventory Report	Approved by the relevant authorities after verification
Water Production Workshop Journal	Accounting of m ³ per day / month / year
Chemical Analysis Journal	Regular tests (salts, metals, radon, etc.)
Microbiology Journal	Level of bacteria, pathogens, etc.

Thus, this period is characterized by institutional content regarding the management of NHA, however, each management body continues to function separately according to its own powers without the coordination of a single policy. NHA accounting and inventory were also not fully integrated.

This period can be characterized as fragmented institutional, because the powers were decentralized between state and regional authorities. Control over the inventory, certification of natural healing assets was carried out at the expense of the owners or selectively by the authorities.

The period of 2020-2022 of the resource-based economy can be characterized by a gradual shift in emphasis on safety, rehabilitation, integration of NHA into the national recovery system, the need for digital inventory and public-private management models (table 9).

Table 9 - Overview of regulatory acts on natural healing assets (NHA) in the period of the resource-based economy

Нормативно-правовий акт	Тематика
Law of Ukraine "On Rehabilitation in the Field of Health Care" 2020 No. 1053-IX	Covers the concepts of "rehabilitation", "rehabilitation assistance", "rehabilitation service"
Draft laws on resort and recreational areas 2020	Requires a special regime for nature use, protection and support of natural healing resources
Licensing conditions for conducting economic activities in medical practices 2020	Defines requirements for sanatoriums that use NHA in medical practice
Law of Ukraine "On Domestic Tourism" (new editions, concept of recovery after COVID-19) 2020	Supports sanatoriums as an element of social and domestic tourism
Order of the Ministry of Environmental Protection and Natural Resources of Ukraine On approval of the Regulations on recreational activities within the territories	Regulates health tourism, resort activities at nature reserve fund facilities

and objects of the nature reserve fund of Ukraine 2022 No. 256	
Law of Ukraine "On the public health system" 2022 No. 2573-IX	Defines the foundations of state health policy, including sanitary protection of resources and public health

The period of 2020-2022, the period of the resource-oriented economy, is characterized by a market economy, while business entities conduct their activities without state subsidies. The governing bodies do not change and consist of the Cabinet of Ministers, the Ministry of Health, the Ministry of Environment, the State Service for Geonadra, the State Service for Food and Consumer Protection, local councils (Fig. 4).

In accordance with the legislation, the inventory also includes a well passport, a geological revaluation act, with subsequent entry of information into electronic accounting in state registers.

From the point of view of management requirements and generalizing the formation of reporting, we have compiled a typical form of accounting for a natural medicinal resource (using the example of mineral water) (mineral water, 2020–2022) (Table 9)

Table 9 - Typical form of accounting for a natural healing assets (using the example of mineral water) (mineral water, 2020–2022)

Document	Purpose
NHA passport (based on MOZ-284)	Resource description, medicinal properties
Report of sanitary inspection of the source	Issued by the State Service for Food and Consumer Protection
Permit for special water use (Ministry of Environment)	Legal basis for PCR sampling
Report of well inventory (State Geological Survey)	Stock balance, debit confirmation
Laboratory control logs	Bacteriology, chemical composition, frequency of analyses
NHA user report	Submission to the State Service for Geology and Mineral Resources / DRSU / local authorities for approval of new operating conditions

Figure 4. Management bodies of the resort economy from the point of view of rehabilitation, health improvement and NHA (period 2020 - 2022)

The management model of this period remained almost unchanged, but changes were made regarding the treatment and rehabilitation of the COVID-19 pandemic.

The main imbalance remained the fragmentation of the institutional system: the Ministry of Health is responsible for the medical aspect, the Ministry of Environment for water use, and sanatoriums for all actual operation, without having ownership of the resource.

Financing for rehabilitation and health needs has found more budget funding through COVID-subsidies in 2020–2021. Improving the NHA management and control system is involved in the implementation of electronic platforms for issuing permits.

The period of the blue economy can be characterized by greater digitalization. The focus on rehabilitation, the restoration of tourism after COVID-19, and the registration of medical resources was also strengthened. For the first time, the integration of rehabilitation into clinical routes was formalized. The NHA register became mandatory for resorts.

Since 2023, the period of (regenerative economy), formulated according to the rehabilitation-integrative approach (table 10), has begun to be established.

Table 10 - Overview of regulatory acts on natural healing assets (NHA) in the period of the regenerative economy

Regulatory and legal act	Topics
Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine On Amendments to Certain Resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine on the Development of Urban Planning Documentation at the Local Level 2024 No. 1557	Defines the sanitary zones of resorts (1–3 degrees)
Order of the Ministry of Health On Approval of Methodological Recommendations for the Development of Provisions on Structural Units on Social Protection of the Population of Local State Administrations and the Organization of Activities of the Territorial Community in the Spheres of Social Protection of the Population and Protection of Children's Rights 2023 No. 263-N	Recommendations on the organization of sanatorium-resort treatment of veterans, disabled people, and war victims
Land Code Rev. 2025	Contains norms on land plots used by sanatoriums, health facilities, and rehabilitation facilities.
Draft Strategy for the Formation and Implementation of State Policy in the Sphere of Ecosystem Services Management for the Period Until 2030	Contains requirements for the stability of payments in the field of environmental protection and the use of natural resources in the long term, provided that the stable state of natural resources and services is maintained

The current regenerative economy management model is characterized by an open economy focused on recovery and with an emphasis on decentralization and mixed financing. Institutional support prevails over the

strengthening of the role of regions, as NHA (Fig. 5) are already a strategic asset for the recovery of regions and integration into the recovery and rehabilitation process. A Single Export Portal has also been created, which provides for greater transparency, however, under martial law, access to the portal is not provided even with a digital signature.

This period has already become more digitalized, all licenses and permits are published on the portal of the Ministry of Environment and the State Service for Geonadra. Accounting and reporting requirements remain unchanged. Inventory - once every 5 years, once a year for sanitary conditions.

The reporting form has remained almost unchanged (using the example of mineral water) (mineral water, 2023–2025) (Table 11)

Figure 5. Management bodies of the resort economy from the point of view of rehabilitation, health improvement and NHA (period 2023 - 2025)

Table 11 – The typical reporting form has remained almost unchanged (using the example of mineral water)

Document	Purpose
Natural healing resource passport	Contains information about the source, type of water, tests, depth, treatment profile
Special water use permit (electronic)	Through the Ministry of Environment Portal or DRSU
Production / consumption log	Internal document of the entity
Well sanitary passport	Issued after laboratory control
Technical inventory report	Assessment of the condition of the facility and suitability for further use
Registration in the e-licensing portal	All special permits must be published online (national register)

This period is characterized by a decentralized and integrated management system, cross-sectoral concentration through international projects and digital transformation. Despite progress in the field of electronic registries and clinical routes, the system remains fragmented and requires the creation of a single coordination base, updating the legislation on resorts, and strengthening institutional monitoring of the use of NHA.

Table 11 Comparative analysis of the management system of natural healing assets, resorts, sanatoriums and rehabilitation

Period	Management model	Advantages	Disadvantages
until 1991 Brown	Centralized (state)	Full control by the Union Ministries, stable budget financing, planned use of resources	Lack of competition and innovation, weak efficiency, tied to allied programs
1991–2005 Transitional	Transitional, partially decentralized	Creation of a national legislative framework (law on resorts, permit system), start of privatization of institutions	Fragmentation of powers, loss of control over part of the PCR, lack of funding
2006–2019 Green (for European integration)	Weak coordination, decentralization without integration	Improvement of the regulatory framework, participation in international programs (GEF, EU4Green), some electronic initiatives	Lack of a single management center, uneven regional coverage, weak monitoring
2020–2022 resource-oriented	Institutional integration, crisis renewal	Law "On Rehabilitation" (1053-IX), start of digital inventory of NHA, expansion of social programs	Military instability, delays in the implementation of electronic registers, lack of specialists
2023–2025 renewable	Inter-sectoral coordination with digital elements	Digital registers of NHA and rehabilitation, increasing the role of the Ministry of Health, Ministry of Veterans, DART, development of rehabilitation standards	Lack of a new version of the law "On resorts", weak vertical control, overload of the local level

The analysis of the institutional support for the use and accounting of NHA, as well as the relevant institutions for the period (1991-2025) is presented in Table 12.

Table 12 – Comparative analysis of the institutional support for the use and accounting of NHA, as well as the relevant institutions for the period (1991-2025)

Criterion	Until 1991	1991–2005	2006–2019	2020–2022	2023–2025
Management system	Centralized, vertical, trade union	Decentralized, fragmented	Bureaucratically regulated, with permissive logic	Operational (COVID, war), crisis	Renewable, electronic, integrated
NHA	People's ownership, no market	State ownership, without effective mechanisms for use	State + permit system	State, operation within the framework of special permits	State, digital accounting, integration into National Plans
Main bodies	Ministry of Health of the USSR, All-Union Central Committee of the Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies, SES	MOH, SES, Ministry of Energy and Resources, local councils	Ministry of Health, State Service for Geology and Nadra, Ministry of Ecology, UkrNII	Ministry of Health, Ministry of Environment, State Service for Geonadra, State Service for Food and Consumer Protection	MoH, Ministry of Reconstruction, Ministry of Environment, military administrations
Form of business	All facilities are state-owned	Partial privatization, municipal structures	State enterprises, municipal and private institutions	Relocation, mixed forms, grants	Public-private models, grant support
NHA accounting	Passport, plan, limit, paper accounting	Partially preserved journals, without a single database	Permit journals, passports, regional databases	Partial electronicization, operational accounting	Full digitization, integration into registries
Quality control	SES, regulated system	SES, local level, without updating methodologies	State Food and Consumer Service, laboratories	Selective laboratory control, acts	Planned inspection, electronic report, openness
Rehabilitation	Prevention, restoration of working capacity	Partial function, funding cut	Available, but without priority	COVID-19 and military rehabilitation	National priority (veterans, victims)
Role of	Powerful	Loss of	Restoration of	Methodological	Scientific

science	research institutes, standards	funding, isolation of science	UkrNII functions, methods	protocols of the Ministry of Health, UkrNII (COVID)	support of rehabilitation programs, modernization of NHA
Institutional coordination	Full subordination to the vertical	Lack of a single body	Functions dispersed	Minimal coordination	Emergence of interdepartmental formats (rehabilitation, NHA)

Over this long-term period, the following trends can be distinguished:

- Transition from centralization to decentralization, functions were transferred from the state to the regional level and digital registers;
- From formalization to electronic accounting (open registers and online platforms);
- Fragmented management: powers are concentrated between the Ministry of Health, the Ministry of Ecology, the Ministry of Economy, the Ministry of Reconstruction;
- In connection with the pandemic and martial law, the rehabilitation value of the use of NHA has gained importance;
- Integration of international cooperation as reconstruction assistance.

Among the main imbalances we have identified:

- Despite the commercialization of services using NHA, ownership remains with the state;
- Exhaustive use of NHA, despite legislative regulations, inventory remains irregular;
- Lack of integration of science into real practice;
- Health and rehabilitation are considered separately from tourism and are not taken into account and coordinated with the development of the resort economy.

These imbalances have led to such contradictions as: NHA are used, depleted, but there are no separate provisions on the protection of NHA, despite the fact that they are a strategic resource, but do not have the status of a strategic object. There are also no requirements for the modernization of wells, a special permit is issued, but a quantitative indicator of the investment security of the well is not required.

Summarizing the analyzed data on the development of resort areas, the use of natural therapeutic assets has revealed numerous institutional problems and imbalances. Historically, the management of natural therapeutic resources has been dispersed between different departments and forms of ownership, which has led to inconsistency and inefficiency.

First, the resort sector has undergone a chaotic transformation: the centralized model has spontaneously changed to a market model, without sufficient reform of institutional principles. A significant part of the sanatoriums has become subordinate to the Ukrprofozdorovytsia, while others have become the property of various ministries and have been privatized. Such fragmentation of ownership has

complicated the formation of a single state policy in the industry. In addition, the infrastructure support for the development of this sector by management structures has not been carried out due to the inconsistency of authorized bodies and the lack of funding. Since control over the use of natural therapeutic assets has been carried out by central authorities due to the limitation of leverage, it has remained ineffective.

Secondly, there was a legislative and regulatory lag. The Law of Ukraine “On Resorts” (2000) laid the legal foundations for the development of the resort sector, but many by-laws, norms and standards remained outdated. Inefficient financing and distribution of services, in particular through state social funds, also continued. As a result, the resort sector did not satisfy the population in terms of rehabilitation and rehabilitation: the number of vouchers provided through social insurance was limited, and the private sector developed slowly. Thirdly, there was a lack of effective institutional changes and coordination between stakeholders. No real deep reforms were implemented in the sanatorium and resort sector, and instead of unbundling, fragments of the old management model were partially adapted for the provision of services and management of natural and healing assets. There is a lack of coordination of the activities of management structures. Institutional imbalances are also manifested in the lack of up-to-date and complete statistics on natural healing assets and the activities of sanatorium and resort facilities. The state cadastre of natural healing resources is maintained intermittently, and the accounting of sanatorium facilities is not centralized, which complicates development planning.

World experience offers various models of management of natural healing assets and the resort sector – from state paternalism to market partnership. Let us consider several examples from different regions (*Ukraine, Europe, Asia, USA*) to identify effective tools: the role of the state, public-private partnership, digital platforms, regulatory approaches, integration into the healthcare system. Thus, the report (*Heat and health in the WHO European Region: updated evidence for effective prevention, 2021a*) covers an overview of the management of natural healing assets in Europe. European countries have a rich tradition of managing natural healing assets and a high level of state participation in the preservation and development of natural healing resources. Many European resorts are integrated into national healthcare systems. For example, in Germany there is an institute called “Kur” – preventive treatment in sanatoriums, which is covered by the health insurance fund upon doctor’s prescription; thus, the state and insurers finance a significant share of resort clients. Similar models operate in the Czech Republic, Hungary, and Poland - spa treatments (baths, mud baths, inhalations) are recognized as part of official medicine, regulated by standards, and resort towns have a special status and subsidies for infrastructure maintenance. The role of the state in Europe is also manifested through strict regulation and administration: regulatory and legislative acts on the definition of protection zones around therapeutic springs, limits on water use, requirements for personnel qualifications. Digital platforms and information centers that combine sanatorium and resort

services have also been introduced. For example, many countries have online booking systems and resort catalogs supported by state travel agencies, which simplifies customer access to information. Public-private partnerships are also actively used in Europe: municipalities or state structures may own natural resources (springs, land plots), but lease them out as concessions or cooperate with private operators. In this way, interests are combined - the private sector ensures effective management and investments, and the state controls the conservation of resources and the availability of services.

The Asian experience of managing natural healing assets (*ASEAN Spa Services Standard, 2016*) is characterized by the active role of the state in supporting the resort sector. In East and Southeast Asian countries, governments consider spa and health tourism as a promising sector of the economy and include it in national tourism development strategies. In Japan, a whole direction of the country's economic development is wellness using hot springs and therapeutic practices. State organizations invest in improving the infrastructure of the resort sector and modernize sanatorium and resort facilities. China and Southeast Asian countries (Thailand, Indonesia, Vietnam) also practice the creation of complexes for the improvement of the population. Public-private partnership in Asia is manifested in the fact that the government provides benefits and land for large resort projects, and private corporations or foreign investors build modern health complexes. Regulatory tools are also being improved: for example, ASEAN countries have developed a single standard for spa services (*ASEAN Spa Services Standard*) to guarantee quality and safety for vacationers. The governance model in Asia is a synthesis of tradition and innovative development, with the state controlling and regulating the activities of the resort sector through legislation, and territorial communities investing and innovating in the sector.

Reports (*Wellness Retreats Market Size & Industry Growth 2030, 2024*) , (History & Culture - Hot Springs National Park (U.S. National Park Service) regarding the management of the natural healing economy and the development of the resort sector in the United States demonstrate an approach different from Europe, which can be characterized as market-oriented and decentralized. The state does not finance sanatoriums as part of the healthcare system. The private basis for the development of this sector began only thanks to wellness. The state regulates only standards (sanitation requirements, licensing of doctors, environmental supervision of national parks). Digital platforms and technologies in the USA play a huge role: American wellness resorts were the first to introduce online booking, virtual spa tours, and actively use CRM systems to work with customers.

EU practice establishes requirements for environmental indicators, extraction and further use of water treatment resources. Member States establish ownership of SPAs, establish requirements for extraction, and carry out certification of SPAs. For example, in Latvia, the SPA management model is similar to the Ukrainian one. The Cabinet of Ministers establishes the status of resort areas, the Ministry of Economy manages the resort sector, the Ministry of Health finances rehabilitation, and the Sanitary and Epidemiological Supervision

monitors the chemical characteristics of water quality. Resource certification (*Guidelines for Drinking-water Quality third edition incorporating the first and second addenda, 2008*) (soft springs, mud, climate) is included in the resort legislation. Standards for natural mineral waters are established by the EU Directive 2009/54/EC for mineral/spring waters (Natural mineral waters and spring water) - regulates mineral water, sanitary standards, certification. Ownership of SPAs is state-owned, however, they are provided for use under concession terms.

French law allows private individuals or companies to own mineral water sources (3 nations seek private input for €2.5bn critical mineral investment, 2024). However, the exploitation of such sources is subject to state control: state authorization is required for drilling or activities within a protected zone: art. L1322 3-10 of the Health Code, sources are declared to be in the “public interest”, protective perimeters are established, and all activities within these limits require the authorization of the state representative of the department.

The Italian legal regime allows for private or public ownership of sources (*The ownership of water resources in Italy, 2015*).

Japan (*Contributors to Wikimedia projects, 2003*) focuses on the preservation and safe operation of owners: it sets requirements for temperature, composition, licenses and accident prevention. PLAs are state or municipally owned.

In India, the BIS regulates water quality standards, including mineral water. (IS 13428:2024, 2024), which involves joint control of their extraction and use by many ministries (health, water, tourism).

In America, the FDA regulates products such as bottled water, which includes mineral water - it sets standards and procedures. (*Bottled Water/Carbonated Soft Drinks Guidance Documents & Regulatory Information, 2022*). The EPA controls the drinking water supply network, there are monitoring systems and annual reports. At the same time, private ownership of PLA located on the ground is allowed.

The experience of managing natural healing assets contains common features. First, the role of the state remains important wherever it comes to protecting unique natural resources and ensuring the quality of services - whether it is direct management or effective regulation and support. Second, public-private partnerships have proven effective in modernizing resort infrastructure: combining the resources and experience of the state and business allows for faster results. Third, digitalization has become a global trend - from Japan to Europe, resorts are implementing online services, which increases their competitiveness. Finally, integration into the healthcare system is the factor that guarantees sustainable demand for resort services. Ukraine, taking into account foreign experience, can build its post-war strategy for managing natural healing assets and the resort sector by combining world experience with its own unique potential of natural healing resources. This will open new prospects for the development of resort areas as an important component of the economy and healthcare system during the reconstruction period.

The positions of the key bodies for the management of natural resources: the Ministry of Environment, the State Service for Geo-nadra, the Ministry of Health and the State Service for Food and Consumer Protection, the distribution of responsibility for the management of natural therapeutic assets, rehabilitation, control, extraction and digitalization is carried out as follows:

- Ministry of Environment: formation and implementation of state policy in the field of environmental protection; geological study, rational use of subsoil, including mineral waters; state environmental control of the use of natural resources; monitoring and assessment of the state of natural resources; approval of technical regulations, standards and accounting of state-owned objects; participation in the digitalization of data through geospatial infrastructure (paragraph 4 of Resolution No. 614).

- State Service for Geo-nadra: licensing and control of natural resources extraction; maintenance of the State Register of deposits and reserves (including therapeutic); geological inventory and certification of deposits; approval of technical documentation (for extraction, development of deposits); implementation of the Unified Geoinformation Platform, publication of interactive cadastres.

- Ministry of Health: approval of medical criteria for the suitability of PCR for treatment; development of rehabilitation standards; monitoring compliance of sanatorium-resort institutions with medical requirements; participation in the formation of a policy on rehabilitation and recovery, implementation of electronic medical documentation, NSZU registers, cooperation with eHealth.

- State Service for the Protection of the Population and Consumers: control of water quality (including drinking, bottled and medicinal); sanitary supervision in places of extraction and use of PLA; inspection of storage, transportation and use conditions of medicinal waters;

- participation in monitoring the safety of PLA and products based on them.

The interaction of these management structures can be determined in Table 13.

Table 13 – Interaction of management structures

Scope	Ministry of Environment	State Geological Survey	Ministry of Health	State Service for Food and Consumer Protection
NHA accounting	+ (environment)	+ (fields and reserves)	—	+ (quality)
Extraction control	+	+	—	—
Rehabilitation use	—	—	+	+
Sanitary control	—	—	+	+
Data digitization	+	+	+ (medical data)	+

Thus, each of the main bodies is responsible for key aspects of the use of NHA, however, the fragmentation of powers complicates interdepartmental coordination.

We consider it necessary to distribute responsibility for the life cycle of NHA between government bodies for clearer relationships and control of the environmental condition and use of NHA at the stages of the life cycle

1. Geological exploration, cartography. Responsible: The State Service of Geology and Subsoil of Ukraine should include:

- Identification of deposits of natural medicinal resources (mineral waters, muds, thermal springs, etc.);
- Conducting hydrogeological, radiological, chemical and physical-mechanical studies;
- Entry into the State Balance of Mineral Resources (in particular, medicinal);
- Creation of a geoinformation model of NHA with open access on the geoportal of the State Service of Geology and Subsoil of Ukraine.
- Financing should be carried out at the expense of license fees and subventions of the Ministry of Finance;

2. Assessment of medical suitability. Responsible: Ministry of Health (MOH)

- Development of methods for assessing the therapeutic effectiveness of sources in accordance with WHO standards;
- Assignment of NHA of a sanatorium-resort profile (for example: sodium, radon);
- Inclusion in the register of facilities suitable for use in rehabilitation and health improvement.

3. Sanitary examination and certification. Responsible: State Service for Food Safety and Consumer Protection (SPCP)

- Annual inspections of sources include analysis of microbiological, sanitary-chemical and toxicological indicators of sources;
- Issuance of a sanitary passport for a facility for the extraction or use of NHA;
- Annual recertification of sources according to international standards (WHO, EU Drinking Water Directive);
- Formation of a database of facilities with valid certification and their availability online.

Costs can be compensated through the special fund of the NHA (from license fees); payment by the NHA users; or the National Health Insurance Fund, when the NHA is included in the rehabilitation procedures.

4. Licensing for mining. Responsible: State Geology and Subsoil Service of Ukraine:

- Holding an auction for the right to use subsoil;
- Issuance of a special permit with a clearly defined volume and mode of mining;
- License conditions include requirements for environmental monitoring, reporting and payment of fees;
- Control of compliance with license conditions.

1. Use for medical purposes. Responsible: Ministry of Health / National Health Service of Ukraine (National Health Service of Ukraine)

- Connection of sanatorium and resort facilities to state medical subvention or contracts with the National Health Service of Ukraine;

- Integration of NHA procedures into the list of guaranteed rehabilitation services;

- Formation of treatment standards based on efficiency analysis (model of France, Czech Republic);

- Requirement for facilities — availability of a source passport and annual reporting.

2. Public control. Responsible: Local communities / local governments

- Involvement of community representatives in environmental impact assessment procedures;

- Granting the community the right to initiate inspections of users of the NHA;

- Maintaining local public registers of NHA indicating users and the level of extraction;

- Cooperation with local governments within the framework of local strategies for the development of resort infrastructure.

3. Digital transparency. Responsible: All bodies in coordination with the Ministry of Digitalization

- Supplementing the Unified State Electronic Geoinformation System for Subsoil Use with the geoinformation component of the NHA;

- Creation of a single electronic platform for reporting, reviewing licenses, and accessing certificates;

- Implementation of the API system for interaction between the Ministry of Health, the State Service for the Study of Natural Resources and Mineral Resources, the National Service for the Study of Natural Resources and Mineral Resources, and local governments;

- Requirement for the publicity of all data that is not a commercial secret.

This expanded model allows for control, efficiency, transparency and adaptability of the NHA management system at all levels - national, regional, local - taking into account the best global practices and standards. Considering the above, we have proposed changes that will allow us to update approaches to NHA management without creating new bodies, using the mechanisms of existing provisions of central government bodies, integrating medical, geological, sanitary and digital components according to the European model.

Regulations on the Ministry of Environment: Approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dated 06/25/2020 No. 614 (Some Issues of the Ministry of Environmental Protection and Natural Resources, 2020)

Changes to paragraph 3 (Main tasks):

Add:

- coordination of environmental impact assessment of NHA facilities;

- approval of environmental standards for the load on NHA and adjacent territories;
- monitoring compliance with the environmental protection regime for the operation of NHA;

Changes to paragraph 4 (Functions):

Add:

- participation in the development of a joint procedure between the Ministry of Health, Geonadra, and the State Service for the Regulation of the Load on NHA Sources;
- conducting an environmental audit of NHA users (once every 3 years);
- coordination of environmental passports of sources in which PLA is used for commercial or recreational purposes.
- creation of an integrated register of the load on NHA in cooperation with the Ministry of Digital Economy.

The Regulation on the State Geology and Subsoil Service of Ukraine (On Approval of the Regulation on the State Geology and Subsoil Service of Ukraine, 2015) was approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dated 30.12.2015 No. 1174

Changes to paragraph 3 (Main tasks):

Add after the subparagraph "maintaining the state register of deposits...":

- implementation of comprehensive mapping and certification of natural medicinal resources (NHA);
- supplement the unified state electronic geoinformation system for subsoil use with the NHA geoinformation model with open access on the Geonadra geoportal;
- inclusion of NHA in the State Balance of Mineral Resources;

Changes to paragraph 4 (Functions):

Add:

- holding auctions for the right to use NHA;
- issuing special permits for NHA extraction with fixing the volumes, terms, conditions of protection and control;
- interaction with the Ministry of Health and the State Service for the Protection of Natural Resources on the profiling and safe use of NHA;

Regulations on the Ministry of Health of Ukraine (On Approval of the Regulations on the Ministry of Health of Ukraine, 2015) Approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dated 25.03.2015 No. 267

Changes to paragraph 3 (Main tasks):

Add after the task on the implementation of state policy in the field of health care:

- methodological support for the medical assessment of NHA (in accordance with WHO);
- assignment of NHA to a sanatorium-resort profile from a medical point of view;
- formation of a list of NHA suitable for use in state rehabilitation programs.

Changes to paragraph 4 (Functions):

Add:

- approval of criteria for assessing the therapeutic effect of NHA;
- integration of NHA into the Medical Guarantees Program (through the National Health Insurance Fund);
- participation in the formation of clinical protocols for rehabilitation based on PLA.

The Regulation on the State Service of Ukraine for Food Safety and Consumer Protection (On Approval of the Regulation on the State Service of Ukraine for Food Safety and Consumer Protection, 2015) was approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dated 02.09.2015 No. 667

Changes to paragraph 3 (Main tasks):

Add after the paragraph on state supervision:

- control of the sanitary quality of NHA at all stages: extraction, transportation, storage, use;
- annual certification of NHA sources in accordance with WHO and EU directives;

Changes to paragraph 4 (Functions):

Add:

- participation in interdepartmental inspections of NHA sources together with Geonadra and the Ministry of Health;
- maintaining a Unified Register of Certified NHA Sources with open access;
- issuing a sanitary passport for a NHA facility.

Appendix to the Regulations of all four bodies in terms of information interaction:

- creation of a unified digital NHA register based on the geoinformation hub of the Ministry of Digital;
- implementation of an API exchange system between Geonadra, the Ministry of Health, the State Social Security Administration, the Ministry of Environment, and the National Health Service;
- obligation of bodies to provide and update data on permits, certificates, and medical reports in the public space.

Financial support can be provided through trust funds (environmental tax), contributions from NHA users, license fees, and funds from the National Health Service for certification and laboratory analysis

CONCLUSIONS

The current institutional system of Ukraine has sufficient potential for effective management of NHA, if the functions of specialized bodies are supplemented by clear interdepartmental mechanisms of interaction, as provided for in the experience of EU countries and GWI.

The institutional division of powers between the Ministry of Health, the State Service for the Study of Natural Resources, the State Service for

Geosciences, the Ministry of Environment and local governments forms a clear vertical and horizontal line of responsibility, avoids duplication of functions and negligent handling of natural therapeutic assets.

The proposed model systematically covers all stages of the NHA life cycle - from geological exploration to medical use - and ensures comprehensive control, supervision, digital openness and medical and environmental compliance.

The coordination mechanism through the Ministry of Digital and the creation of an open geoportal with public registers of certified sources, permits, environmental passports and medical reports guarantees transparency for society and business.

International WHO standards, EU directives, practices of Germany, Japan, Czech Republic are adapted to the national context, which ensures the possibility of implementation without changing the legislative framework (through amendments to the by-laws - regulations of the ministries).

The financing of the system can be diversified: through the mechanisms of the National Health Service, license fees, paid certification services, special funds of the Ministry of Environment - without the need for additional budgetary burden.

Public and local control becomes a real tool for influencing the processes of extraction, licensing and sanitary supervision thanks to open data and the involvement of communities in decision-making.

The implementation of a digital model of NHA management will increase the investment attractiveness of the resort economy, provide transparency for international donors and allow for the effective integration of NHA into post-war reconstruction and development programs.

The practical significance of the results obtained is as follows:

- The results of the study can be used to develop state policy on the NHA in the context of post-war recovery and the development of medical rehabilitation.
- The proposed additions can be directly included in draft orders, resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine or interdepartmental regulations.
- The developed model allows for the effective use of the potential of the NHA in state programs of rehabilitation, tourism and economic growth of regions.

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